

Stability Constants of Iron(III), Chromium(III) and Aluminium(III) Chelates with some Substituted Pyrazoles

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Metal chelates of 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylisoxazoline with Be^{II} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} , and UO_2^{II} have been investigated by Khadilkar *et al.*¹. Narwade *et al.*² studied the stability constants of complexes of Th^{IV} with some substituted pyrazolines potentiometrically. Murthy *et al.*³ studied the metal-ligand stability constants with some substituted isoxazoles. Mahajan and Narwade⁴ studied Cu^{II} complexes with sulphonic acid potentiometrically. Narwade *et al.*⁴ also studied stability constants of Cu^{II} complexes with some substituted pyrazolines and isoxazolines.

In view of analytical applications, it was of an interest to know the physicochemical properties such as stability constants of the complexes with Fe^{III} , Cr^{III} and Al^{III} metal ions. Moreover, the studies on stability constants of the above trivalent metal ions with some substituted pyrazoles are lacking. It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the chelating properties of some other substituted pyrazoles. In the present work, the interactions of Fe^{III} , Cr^{III} and Al^{III} metal ions with 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenylpyrazole (HPPPPZOLE), and 3-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-5-phenylpyrazole (HMPPPPZOLE) and 3-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrazole (HMPMPPZOLE) have been investigated potentiometrically in 70% dioxane-water mixture as a solvent at 0.1 M ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants : Substituted pyrazoles may be considered as monobasic acids having only one replaceable H^+ ion from phenolic group and can, therefore, be represented as HL. It is observed from the titration curves that the ligand curves start deviating from the free acid curves at about pH 7.0. The deviation increased continuously

upto pH 11.5. It indicated that OH group starts to dissociate at about pH 7.0 and completes its dissociation at about pH 11.0.

The proton-ligand formation numbers (\bar{n}_A) were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's expression. The pK values were estimated from formation curves (\bar{n}_A vs pH) by noting the pH at which $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The accurate values of pK were determined by pointwise calculations which are presented in Table 1. The pK values are found to increase in the following order of ligands : HMPMPPZOLE > HMPPPPZOLE > HPPPPZOLE. It may be attributed to the increasing electron-releasing tendencies of the groups (CH_3 , OCH_3).

Metal-ligand stability constants : The stability constants of the Fe^{III} , Cr^{III} and Al^{III} complexes with some substituted pyrazoles were determined employing Bjerrum pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti.

The formation of chelate between Fe^{III} , Cr^{III} , Al^{III} and the pyrazoles was indicated by (i) the significant departure, starting from pH 2.0 to 2.5, of metal complex titration curves from the ligand curves and (ii) the change in colour from light yellow brown to dark brown as pH was raised from 2.0 to 7.0. The log K values were directly read from the formation curves (\bar{n}_A vs pH) using half-integral method. The most accurate log K values were calculated by pointwise calculation (Table 1). For all the systems, the log K_1 and log K_2 values follow the order as $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} > \text{Cr}^{\text{III}} > \text{Al}^{\text{III}}$. This order has been followed by 5 SSA, EDTA, pyridine-2-carboxylic acid and Tiron⁶. The complexes of Fe^{III} are stable than those of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} . This is because Fe^{III} is a hard acid while Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} are borderline cases⁷.

It could also be seen (Table 1) that log K values follow decreasing trend. This is due to the

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE PYRAZOLES AND THE COMPLEXES

Ionic Strength = 0.1 M

Compd.	pK				
HPPPZOLE	10.40 ± 0.020				
HMPPPZOLE	10.55 ± 0.035				
HMPMPPZOLE	10.60 ± 0.025				
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_3	(log K_1 - log K_2)	log K_1 / log K_2
Fe ^{III} -HPPPZOLE	11.80	11.35	10.75	0.45	1.039
Fe ^{III} -HMPPPZOLE	11.65	9.70	5.25	1.95	1.201
Fe ^{III} -HMPMPPZOLE	11.50	10.90	7.25	0.60	1.055
Cr ^{III} -HPPPZOLE	11.25	8.25	7.45	3.00	1.363
Cr ^{III} -HMPPPZOLE	11.60	8.90	8.00	2.70	1.303
Cr ^{III} -HMPMPPZOLE	11.00	8.55	7.70	2.45	1.286
Al ^{III} -HPPPZOLE	10.60	9.85	5.10	0.75	1.076
Al ^{III} -HMPPPZOLE	10.75	10.30	9.50	0.45	1.043
Al ^{III} -HMPMPPZOLE	10.55	10.25	7.45	0.30	1.029

effect of electron-releasing groups (CH₃, OCH₃). The values of log K (log K_1 - log K_2) and log K_1 /log K_2 are presented in Table 1. It is observed that one would expect a bigger difference between log K_1 and log K_2 values in such ligands of possible steric hindrance to the linking of the secondary ligand to the metal ion. The small difference may be due to *trans*-structure. The results show that the ratio log K_1 /log K_2 is positive in all cases.

Separation factor between the first and second formation constants are well within the expected range and absence of high values imply that there is little or no steric hindrance to the addition to secondary ligand molecule.

Validity of (log $K = a$ pK + b) relation: The linear relation, log $K = a$ pK + b has been found out by some workers⁸ to hold for transition metal complex of a series of closed related ligands.

The stability of the metal complexes of substituted pyrazoles follows the order: Fe^{III} > Cr^{III} > Al^{III}.

The plots of log K_1 /log K_2 vs pK show satisfactory linear relationship giving slope values of 1.03 and 1.08 respectively. The partial molar free energies of metal-ligand and proton-ligand complexes exactly compensate each other, when log K vs pK plot is linear with a slope of unity.

Experimental

Metal nitrates (B.D.H.) were dissolved in perchloric acid and their concentrations were estimated by standard method⁹. Substituted pyrazoles were prepared from the appropriate 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-1,3-propanediones and hydrazine hydrate in ethanol¹⁰. Pyrazoles are insoluble in water and hence dioxane-water (70%, v/v) was used as solvent. 1,4-Dioxane was purified by standard method¹¹ and its purity was checked by potassium iodide.

pH measurements were carried out with an Elico-LI-10 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.05 unit) using glass and calomel electrodes at 27 ± 0.10°. The B values (pH meter readings in 70% dioxane-water mixture) were converted to [H⁺] values by applying the concentrations proposed by Van-Uitert and Haas¹².

The overall 0.1 M ionic strength of the solution was calculated by the expression,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1} C_i Z_i^2$$

The contribution of the other ions in addition to Na⁺ and ClO₄⁻ were also taken into consideration.

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